

Ten years on the IUPAP Commission on Particles and Fields

by Edwin Goldwasser

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My participation with the IUPAP Commission on Particles and Fields started in 1970 when Bob Wilson and I (then Fermilab Director and Deputy Director respectively) proposed to host the XVIth International Conference on High Energy Physics at Fermilab in 1972. The Conference was eventually held in the Fermilab auditorium, then still under construction (Parke Rohrer, Manager of the Laboratory's architect-engineering firm, spent the night before the Conference caulking the auditorium roof to stop the leaks). During the following year I was elected to serve a three year term as one of the two US representatives on the Commission. Frank Yang (USA) was then Chairman and when he was succeeded by Bernard Gregory (France). I was elected Secretary. On the tragic and unexpected death of Bernard Gregory, I was asked to act in his place as Chairman.

Six years is the normal limit in terms of service on the Commission, but in 1978 a number of important problems were unresolved and the other members requested the General Assembly of IUPAP that I be elected for one more term. The request was accepted and my third term was completed last year.

One of the notable features of the decade was a transition from an age of plenty to an age of scarcity for research in general, and for high energy physics in particular. The impact of the change in the world economy was felt more acutely in the arena of international scientific cooperation than in other scientific activities.

In 1972 there was an insistent call for a proliferation of international conferences on high energy physics. New developments seemed to be too rapid for the journals to respond. The principal means of communication was becoming preprints or short

'letters'. Such communications alone were not completely satisfactory and physicists were finding that a valuable medium was presentation at a conference where active physicists could compare notes, criticize interpretations, develop new ideas, and even arrange new collaborations.

With the increasing size and complexity of facilities, experimental groups had increased in size. Furthermore, with the increasing cost of such facilities, there was pressure to avoid duplication. Large facilities first involved the joint effort of a number of scientists at a single institution. Then came inter-institutional cooperation. Finally, international teams have become common. That last step requires a suitable forum where people can meet to discuss their interests and ideas.

It has always been my belief that such conferences also serve an almost independent purpose in the sphere of international relations. If we are to develop a better understanding among nations, nothing is more important than improving communication. IUPAP sponsorship has been important in the development of fuller participation in international conferences. Such sponsorship is recognized in many nations as an indication of the value and appropriateness of a conference.

With the tightening of research budgets during the past decade, the atmosphere surrounding the previous proliferation of conferences gradually changed. The choice whether to invest funds in foreign travel or in research equipment and operations became more difficult. Sponsoring agencies in a number of countries established tighter controls over foreign travel. Valuable as international conferences may be, it is understandable to look at them as peripheral to the 'real' conduct of

research. I believe this jeopardizes the effectiveness of research in our era. It also poses a real threat to one of the fragile threads of international cooperation.

As funding decreased, those authorities and agencies who screen or sponsor foreign travel leaned more heavily on the symbol of IUPAP's sponsorship as an indicator of the importance of conferences in high energy physics. This responsibility has become increasingly evident and the Commission is more selective in its sponsorship, tending to limit it to those conferences which are vital to the vigour of the scientific enterprise and to the health of international cooperation. The Commission has felt that the symbol of IUPAP sponsorship must be protected in order to maintain its value as an 'imprimatur', accepted by many national authorities as an indicator that visas should be issued and travel supported.

Today, the Commission reserves its sponsorship, in the main, for three series. One is the biennial International Conference in High Energy Physics (the 'Rochester Conference'). Another is the biennial International Symposium on Leptons and Photons at High Energies, held in alternate years to the Rochester Conference. Finally there is the International Conference on High Energy Accelerators whose frequency has decreased to once every three years since accelerator developments have slowed.

Each of these series falls within the spirit of the general IUPAP guidelines, and gives good coverage to the field with a time frequency matched to the rate of developments. They do not give as much in-depth coverage as can be realized through small topical conferences, but these are still held on an ad hoc basis, usually without IUPAP sponsorship.

Attendance at IUPAP conferences has always been a sensitive issue. Their importance is widely recognized and leading scientists usually attend. Because of the working nature of the conferences and because of the unique forum they present, active physicists feel they 'must' be there. Unfortunately, because their effectiveness seems to many to hinge upon a limitation on the number of participants, attendance has traditionally been by invitation. This has made it possible to maintain appropriate international representation.

It has been traditional to give the organizer the broadest possible autonomy in arranging the conference. However during the past decade it became clear, in particular with the Rochester series, that the interests of international participation would be furthered if the Commission took responsibility for the national quotas. On several occasions, an

organizing committee arbitrarily reduced the traditional representation of some other nation. On one occasion during Bernard Gregory's chairmanship, one organizing committee arbitrarily halved the Commission-established quota for another nation. After other appeals had been ineffective, Gregory and I had to indicate that IUPAP sponsorship would be withdrawn unless the problem was rectified and the quota was restored. The Commission has therefore established detailed quotas which are transmitted to the conference host.

There has been an increasing sentiment in the USA against the exclusivity implied by the practice of participation by invitation only. IUPAP representatives from elsewhere still tended to believe that practical considerations limit attendance. The 1980 Rochester Conference was scheduled to be held in the United States, and there were two proposals. The first came from the University of Wisconsin on condition that they could experiment with an 'open conference' format. A California group submitted a second proposal to host the conference on an invitational basis. The Commission finally decided for Madison, under the condition that provision would nevertheless have to be made for the established international quotas. The Wisconsin group, in consultation with the Commission, devised procedures which made it possible both to maintain national quotas and to make the conference effectively open to all. The Commission was pleased with the result and now encourages such open conferences.

Another major development in the activities of the Commission has been the decision to sponsor a new committee which concerns itself with the long range future. This International Committee on Future Accel-

erators (ICFA) has its roots in a series of meetings of laboratory directors, physicists, and officials, culminating in a meeting in New Orleans in 1975. The subject was 'Perspectives in High Energy Physics'. During that meeting it was noted that the progress of high energy physics, in the next decade, would almost certainly require an accelerator and experimental facilities so large that they could not be built by an individual nation or region. It was recognized also that the technical, organizational, economic and political problems connected with the formation of a 'world' laboratory would be formidable. It was suggested that a study be started to consider the next large high energy physics development, then seen about a decade in the future. The facility was named the Very Big Accelerator (VBA).

After some preliminary meetings, the informal study group established at the New Orleans meeting approached the Commission requesting sponsorship for the formation of ICFA. In 1976 the Commission agreed and it was decided that ICFA should have three members from CERN Member States, three from the Soviet Union, three from the USA, one from Japan, and one from Dubna Member States (other than the Soviet Union). The Chairman of the IUPAP-Commission was designated to be a twelfth member, *ex officio*. The Commission defined ICFA responsibilities 'to organize workshops for the study of problems related to an international super high energy accelerator complex (VBA) and to elaborate the framework of its construction and use; to organize meetings for the exchange of information on future plans of regional facilities and for the formulation of advice on joint studies and uses.' ICFA elects its own chairman. Before he died, Bernard Gregory had been chosen to

The University of Wisconsin-Madison, scene of the 1980 'Rochester' Conference, which dispensed with the traditional rule of participation by invitation only.

(Photo University News Service)

be the first. John Adams was elected to replace him.

In its first five years ICFA has organized more than a half a dozen meetings and workshops to consider the physics motivation for the construction of a VBA, possible designs and limitations, and developments in detectors, magnets, and instrumentation. It has also been agreed that there should be a meeting on some of the political, economic and organizational problems associated with the establishment of an international laboratory. ICFA has been successful in stimulating the kind of discussion which must occur prior to any serious planning for the VBA. On the other hand, the world economy has faltered and the original lead time of one decade from 1975 was clearly too short.

Another development during the past decade is the reestablishment of communications with the People's

Republic of China. China indicated an interest in high energy physics and the Commission responded immediately with an invitation to join. Although there has been much friendly conversation, the Chinese have not yet engaged in the activities of the Commission. They are reluctant because IUPAP recognizes Taiwan as an active participant in its affairs. Sporadic discussions are still in progress, and it is hoped that China will enter into the activities of IUPAP and ICFA in the near future.

During my decade on the Commission, the most troublesome problem has been the inability of conference organizers to arrange for the participation of some of the outstanding physicists from the USSR. A ten year survey showed that whereas 95 per cent of speakers invited from other nations had accepted invitations to speak at IUPAP-sponsored conferences, less than 30 per cent of those

invited from the USSR had similarly been able to accept and attend the conferences. In response to a series of problems faced by conference organizers and in response to the results of its ten year survey, the Commission, at its 1978 meeting in Tokyo, therefore passed the following resolution:

'At all conferences sponsored by the IUPAP Commission on Particles and Fields every endeavour must be made to ensure that the best qualified scientists from all regions are able to attend. The foundation of the Commission's programme of major meetings has, in the past, been a regular rotation of the venue among those regions actively engaged in high energy physics research. The principle of a parity of rotation is only meaningful if there is a corresponding parity in the participation at the conferences by scientists who are most actively engaged in the research to be discussed. The Commission's established policy must necessarily be placed in jeopardy if any nation or region is judged by the Commission not to be contributing its fair share to the scientific exchange. The Commission will not normally choose such a nation or region as a site for any conferences.'

Since this resolution was passed there have been three major conferences sponsored by the Commission. In each case, the conference organizers were unable to get the same kind of participation from invited Soviet scientists as is traditional from scientists of other nations.

Normal procedure dictated that a site for the 1984 Rochester Conference should be chosen at the 1981 meeting of the Commission in Bonn. In accordance with the usual rotation among the three major regions, the 1984 Conference normally would

People and things

have been scheduled for the USSR. However there was substantial support of the Tokyo resolution by high energy physicists in the United States and in Europe.

At the Bonn meeting, a tentative invitation was submitted by East Germany, proposing that the 1984 Conference be held in Leipzig. The Commission accepted that invitation on a provisional basis, pending a satisfactory response to the usual questions which were answered at the Commission meeting in conjunction with the 1982 Rochester Conference in Paris. Just before retiring as Chairman, I wrote to Anatoly Alexandrov, President of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR, and to Andrei Petrosyants, Chairman of the USSR State Committee for Utilization of Atomic Energy. In that letter I indicated my own thoughts as follows:

'I would not be completely honest if I did not inform you about my own ideas about the future, recognizing, of course, that my official responsibility for these matters is now coming to an end. Of course I join all of my colleagues in hoping that USSR participation in international conferences will soon become indistinguishable from the participation of other IUPAP members... You have my very best wishes for success in your continued efforts to further the goals of science in the USSR. The potential for major contributions in high energy physics from the Soviet Union is great, and the potential for achievement by the gradually developing international community of scientists is greater yet. The potential of each of us can be magnified manyfold if we join hands in a common effort. But such an effort requires the full and free participation of the best scientists, no matter from where they come. Not only does such a cooperative effort enhance the progress of science, but it also

contributes significantly to the prestige of those nations whose scientists are able to push the frontiers of knowledge still further ahead. On the other hand, any nation which frustrates the efforts of its scientists and handicaps them in their activities not only sets back the progress of science, in general, but also deals itself a costly blow in world prestige, in its ability to contribute to the advancement of science, and in its ability to exploit the full potential of its own scientific talent.'

Dame Margaret Weston, Director of the Science Museum in London, gives the opening address at the inauguration of a CERN exhibition at the Museum, open until the end of November. Left is William Shelton, Under Secretary of State at the UK Department of Education and Science, who formally inaugurated the exhibition, and right is CERN Director General Herwig Schopper.

(Photo 531.9.82)

On people

Paul Reardon, at present heading construction of the Tokamak Fusion Test Reactor (TFTR) project at the Princeton Plasma Physics Laboratory, is to move to Brookhaven where amongst his responsibilities will be leadership of the ISABELLE project (now, in view of its likely reformulation — see October issue, page 318 — usually referred to as the Colliding Beam Accelerator, CBA). He has extensive previous experience at Princeton, MIT (where he headed the team that built the electron linac) and Fermilab (where he headed Booster construction and was later Technical Director).

Meetings

The 11th International Symposium on Lepton-Photon Interactions at

